

Resilience Tracker Sheets

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections

Total Resilience Points:

Resilience Chart How many Challenges did you complete? Compare your results to this table and **celebrate!**

Complete 2 Challenges = Resilience Masters

Complete 3 Challenges = Resource Guardians

Complete 4 Challenges = Solidarity Squad

Complete 5 Challenges = Mutual Aid Commanders

Complete 6 Challenges = Queerfeminist Rebels

Why not compare the collaboratively earned RPs against your score from the last time you played and **discuss** what was different this time.

Example Resilience Tracker table:

Resilience Points	Reason	Card Title	Action Identified	Takeaways/Reflections
+ 5	Starting points	n/a	Play RESIST/ANCE!	I thought the game was...
+ 1	<i>Strategy Action</i>	<i>"Legal Counselling"</i>	<i>Contact ...</i>	<i>It became clear that...</i>
- 1	<i>Event card</i>	<i>"Abandonment"</i>	<i>Write down the...</i>	<i>The process which...</i>
+ 7	<i>Challenge Overcome</i>	<i>"Legal Intimidation"</i>	<i>A pattern of...</i>	<i>It would be good to reach out to...</i>
+ 1	<i>Event Card</i>	<i>"Speaking Up to Push Back..."</i>	<i>Consider...</i>	<i>It can be so difficult to...</i>
- 2	<i>Toolkit refill</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>It was worth refilling because...</i>
Total: 11RPs				

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RESIST/ANCE—Strategies for a Better World

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